

SOME PHYSICO-CHEMICAL AND METALS ANALYSIS OF FIVE WELL WATER AT UJEH IN IBAJI LGA, KOGI STATE

Inikpi Ojochide Egwemi

Department of Science Laboratory Technology,
Federal Polytechnic, Idah, Kogi state
Email: ojochidemary2015@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Five water samples, labeled A, B, C, D and E were collected from five different water well in Ujeh, IbaJI LGA in Kogi state. Some physico-chemical characteristics and the concentrations of some metals were determined using standard procedures. The results of the analysis of the physico-chemical parameters of the samples analysed were in the following range; pH (6.05 ± 0.02 to 6.31 ± 0.02), Turbidity (0 ± 0.29 NTU to 20.83 ± 0.76 NTU), Electrical conductivity (2.67 ± 0.58 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ to 10.00 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), TDS (from 60 ± 20 mg/L to 653.33 ± 30.55 mg/L), CaCO_3 , Chloride (13.93 ± 0.25 mg/L to 26.83 ± 0.25 mg/L), Nitrate (0.42 ± 0.01 mg/L to 0.61 ± 0.01 mg/L), Calcium hardness (15.49 ± 0.42 mg/L to 35.67 ± 0.14 mg/L), Sulphate (0.91 ± 0.12 mg/L to 4.56 ± 0.6 mg/L), Phosphate (7.8 ± 0.11 mg/L to 11.02 ± 0.22 mg/L) and Dissolved oxygen (5.23 ± 0.15 mg/L to 6.5 ± 0.17 mg/L). The metals were determined with Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer AAS Perkin Elmer A. The samples contained Na (1.9 ± 0.1 mg/L to 3.12 ± 0.08 mg/L) and Fe (0.16 ± 0.02 mg/L to 0.37 ± 0.02 mg/L). Pb was not detected in samples A, B and E but found in samples C and D at the concentration of 0.01 ± 0.00 mg/L each. Cd was only found in sample C (0.01 mg/L ± 0.01 mg/L). Cr was below the detection limit in samples A, B and E but was found in samples C (0.02 ± 0.00 mg/L) and D (0.01 ± 0.01 mg/L). All the samples contained Zn (0.29 ± 0.01 mg/L to 0.42 ± 0.02 mg/L).

Keywords: *Physico-chemical parameters, concentrations, Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer, Total hardness, standard procedures*

INTRODUCTION

All forms of plant and animal life depend on water (Fakai et al., 2023). Water plays many different roles in daily life and is a vital component of human nutrition, either directly as drinking water or indirectly as a component of food (Tongu et al., 2024). There are two main natural sources of water: surface water, which includes fresh water, lakes, rivers,

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streams, etc., and ground water, which includes well and borehole water (Fakai et al., 2023). The groundwater offers a valued fresh water resources to human population and creates about two-third of the fresh water reserves presently occupying various spaces across the world (Adeyemi et al., 2017). Untreated water from sources, such as rivers, reservoirs, springs, streams, water wells, and boreholes are used for drinking and other domestic purposes in developing countries because a large portion of the population lacks access to potable water supply (Martínez-Hernández et al., 2020). Chemical contaminants occur in drinking water throughout the world which could possibly threaten human health (Ezeribe et al., 2012).

Today human activities are constantly adding industrial, domestic and agricultural wastes to ground water reservoirs at alarming rate (Aremu et al., 2011). Health problems can arise from consuming contaminated well water. Well water testing can help prevent negative health outcomes associated with consuming contaminated water (Munene et al., 2020). Water quality refers to the chemical, physical, and biological characteristics of water centered on the standards of its usage (Nuri & Adamu., 2023). The quality of groundwater is generally stable over time as it is predominantly determined by the chemical composition of the rocks serving as aquifer (Jidauna et al., 2013). The quality of groundwater resource depends on the management of human waste as well as the natural physico-chemical characteristics of the catchment areas (Abbas et al., 2014). Also, depending on the geology of an area underground waters are typically rich in dissolved solids especially carbonates, sulphate, calcium and magnesium. Other ions may also be present including chlorides and bicarbonates (Abbas et al., 2014).

Drinking water quality standard ensures the safety of the drinking water supplies and the protection of public health (NSDQW, 2015). To determine the quality of water, several parameters must be examined. Among the key parameters listed by World Health Organization (WHO) for the determination of water quality are conductivity, dissolved oxygen (DO), pH, color of water, taste and odour, turbidity, total suspended solids (TSS) chemical oxygen demand (COD), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), micro-organisms such as faecal coliform bacteria (*Escherichia coli*), *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia lamblia*; nutrients (fertilizers), dissolved metals and metalloids (lead, mercury, arsenic and so on) and dissolved organics (WHO, 2011; Olukosi et al., 2016)

Most people in Ujeh in Ibaji Local Government Area of Kogi State, Nigeria depend on well water as an available water source for drinking and domestic purposes, and the qualities of these well water are not guaranteed. The aim of this research is to obtain the physico-chemical characteristics and concentrations of some metals of the five well waters collected from Ujeh and then compare the results with Nigerian Standard for Drinking Water Quality (NSDWQ,2015) and World Health Organization (WHO,2011 and 2017) guideline for drinking water quality.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample Collection

A total of five well water samples were collected from five water well (i.e one sample from a well.) in Ujeh, Ibaji Local Government area, kogi state. The water samples were collected using hard plastic and screw-capped bottles that have been sterilized to avoid contamination by any physical, chemical or microbial means. The collected well water samples were transferred into sterile containers and then taken to the laboratory (Amadi & Olasehinde, 2010).

Physico-chemical Parameters Determination.

Determination of pH

The pH was measured by Electrometric Method using Laboratory pH Meter Hanna model HI991300 (APHA, 2005).

Determination of Turbidity

The turbidity of the samples was measured in the laboratory using the LABTECH DIGITAL turbidity meters. The values were read out directly in Nephelometric units (NTU) after the instrument had been standardized using already-prepared standard.

Determination of Electrical Conductivity

Conductivity meter DDS 307 was used. The probe of the instrument was rinsed with distilled water and then dipped into the sample. It was allowed for sometimes for the reading to stabilize and the reading was recorded.

Determination of Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)

The samples were evaporated and dried in weighed dishes at 105 °C to constant weight; the increase in weight over the empty dish representing the solid content. 100 mL of the samples were used, and the evaporating dishes

were left to cool in desiccators before the weightings were done. The result was expressed in milligram total solids per liter of samples.

Determination of Dissolved Oxygen (DO)

The instrument (portable dissolved oxygen analyser model JPB-607) was switched on and the probe was dipped into the sample for 5 minutes for the reading to stabilize. The reading was then recorded.

Determination of Phosphate

The ascorbic acid method according to APHA (2005) was adopted for the determination of phosphate level of the Well water. Ascorbic acid-based reagent powdered pillow was added into 25 mL of the water sample in a cuvette. The sample was allowed to stand for 2 minutes for reaction to occur. The absorbance and concentration in mg/L was read at 890 nm wavelength using HACH DR 2010 UV-visible spectrophotometer.

Determination of Sulphate

The barium chloride (turbidometric) method by APHA (2005) was adopted. The barium chloride-based powdered reagent pillow was added into 25 ml of water sample. The mixture was properly mixed and allowed to stand for 5 minutes for the reaction to occur. The absorbance and concentration in mg/l was read at 450 nm wavelength using HACH DR 2010 UV-visible spectrophotometer.

Determination of Nitrate

The cadmium reduction method as adapted from APHA (2005) was used in the determination of nitrate levels of the samples. A cadmium-based reagent pillow was added into 25 ml of the water sample in a cuvette and shaken for 1 minute, then allowed to stand for another 5 minutes for the complete reaction to occur. The absorbance and concentration in mg/L was read at 500 nm wavelength using HACH DR 2010 UV-visible spectrophotometer.

Determination of chloride (Mohr's method)

50 mL of water was pipetted into 250 mL conical flask. 1 mL of the indicator (phenolphthalein) was added and titrated with silver nitrate solution until a permanent brick red was obtained.

Ca-Hardness

50 mL of water was pipetted into 250 mL conical flask. 1 mL of sodium hydroxide (8%) and a pinch of mercrex powder was added. It was titrated with standard EDTA solution until the light pink colour of the solution was converted into light blue colour.

Determination of elements

The elements were determined with Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer AAS Perkin Elmer A with flame temp. 2800 and acetylene pressure of 0.9-1.0 bar. The standard solutions were 1000 mg/L, the lamps were standard hollow cathode lamp and the reading was 3-4 sec (max, 10 sec) 0.00 = below detection limit.

Results and Discussion of results

The results obtained for various tests carried out on the physicochemical properties and some metal analysis of the well water samples and their comparison with the World Health Organization (WHO) and Nigerian Standard for Drinking Water Quality (NSDWQ) standard specified for drinking water are contained in Table 1 below. The table shows the mean and standard deviation values of the parameters determined in the research along with the recommended standards.

Table 1: Physicochemical properties and some metal analysis of the well water samples and their comparison with the World Health Organization (WHO) and NSDWQ standard specified for drinking water

PROPERTIES	JUMMAH WELL (A)	GODWIN WELL (B)	TOWN HALL WELL (C)	SCHOOL WELL (D)	ODIUGOWU WELL (E)	NSWD Q 2015	WHO
pH	6.31±0.02	6.23±0.03	6.07±0.04	6.24±0.01	6.05±0.02	6.5-8.5	6.5-8.5
Turbidity	1.25±0.09	0.67±0.29	20.83±0.76	19±0.5	0±0.29	5.0	4
Electrical conductivity	5.67±0.85	5±0.00	10±0.00	8.33±0.58	2.67±0.58	1000	
TDS	86.67±11.55	60±0.00	653.33±30.55	573.33±11.55	60±20	500	600-1000

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	JUMMAH WELL	GODWIN WELL	TOWN HALL WELL	SCHOOL WELL	ODIUGO WU	NSDWQ	WHO
CaCO ₃	12.4±0.35	8.27±0.31	10.27±0.46	9.13±0.23	6.07±0.50		
Chloride	20.08±0.40	22.17±0.28	26.83±0.25	17.70±0.29	13.93±0.25	250	
Nitrate	0.48±0.00	0.46±0.00	0.61±0.01	0.55±0.1	0.42±0.01	50	50
Calcium hardness	30.75±0.25	33.92±0.14	30.38±0.13	35.67±0.14	15.49±0.42		
Sulphate	1.49±0.09	2.4±0.16	4.16±0.14	4.56±0.06	0.91±0.12	100 250-	
Phosphate	8.76±0.11	9.58±0.15	11.02±0.22	10.51±0.13	7.8±0.11		
Dissolved oxygen	5.23±0.15	6.17±0.06	5.73±0.12	6.5±0.17	5.57±0.12	5.0	
Na mg/L	2.2±0.1	3.03±0.06	2.8±0.1	3.12±0.08	1.9±0.1	200	200
Ca mg/L	7.2±0.17	10.57±0.21	9.23±0.12	11.33±0.56	5.33±0.15		
K mg/L	0.45±0.02	0.5±0.00	0.77±0.2	0.82±0.03	0.40±0.03		
Fe mg/L	0.16±0.02	0.25±0.02	0.37±0.02	0.32±0.02	0.25±0.18	0.30	0.3
Pb mg/L	0	0	0.01±0.00	0.01±0.01	0	0.01	0.01
Cd mg/L	0	0	0.01±0.01	0	0	0.003	0.003
Cr mg/L	0	0	0.02±0.00	0.01±0.01	0	0.05	0.05
Zn mg/L	0.29±0.01	0.34±0.02	0.31±0.01	0.42±0.02	0.39±0.02	3	3

Discussion of Results

Turbidity: Turbidity, typically expressed as nephelometric turbidity units (NTU), describes the cloudiness of water caused by suspended particles (e.g. clay and silts), chemical precipitates (e.g. manganese and iron), organic particles (e.g. plant debris) and organisms. Turbidity can be caused by poor source water quality, poor treatment and, within distribution systems, disturbance of sediments and biofilms or the ingress of dirty water through main breaks and other faults (WHO,2022). The turbidity of ground water is generally very low because of the natural filtration that occurs as water penetrates through the ground. From table 1 above, the turbidity content of the five wells water (A to E) ranged from 0±0.29 NTU to 20.83±0.76 NTU.. Sample E had the lowest value of turbidity of 0±0.29 NTU while sample C had the highest turbidity of 20.83±0.76 NTU followed by sample D with 19±0.5 NUT. The turbidity of all the well water samples were within the permissible limit of 0.3 NUT - 25 NUT that was recommended by WHO (2017) for safe drinking water.

Electrical Conductivity (EC)

The electrical conductivity (EC) of water is a measure of the ability of a solution to carry or conduct an electrical current (Nayla Hassan Omer,

2019). Therefore, it is one of the main parameters used to determine the suitability. The results of the analysis shown in the table above showed that the mean conductivity value of all the water samples ranged from $2.67 \pm 0.58 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ to $10.00 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. These values were within the permissible limit ($1000 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) recommend by NSDWQ. No health impact.

Total Dissolved Solid (TDS)

Total dissolved solids (TDS) is a measure of the dissolved combined content of all inorganic and organic substances present in a liquid in ionized, molecular, or micro granular suspended form. TDS is used as an indication of aesthetic characteristics of drinking water and as an aggregate indicator of the presence of chemical contaminants. TDS comprise of inorganic salts, principally calcium, magnesium, potassium, sodium bicarbonates, chlorides and sulphates and some small amounts of organic matter that are dissolved in water (Lila et al,2023).The TDS of the well water analysed ranges from $60 \pm 00 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$ to $653.33 \pm 30.55 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$. These values were within $500 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$, and $600\text{-}1000 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$ recommend by NSDWQ (2015) and WHO (2017) respectively.

pH

pH is one of the most important parameters of water quality. Safe ranges of pH for drinking water are from 6.5 to 8.5 for domestic use and living organisms need .It is defined as the negative logarithm of the hydrogen ion concentration (Spellman FR, 2017; Edward JK, 2010). The results of the analysis in table 2 above showed that PH ranged from 6.05 ± 0.02 to 6.31 ± 0.02 . These results were a little below the minimum desirable limits of 6.5-8.5 recommended by NSDWQ and WHO

Chloride

Chloride occurs naturally in groundwater, streams, and lakes, but the presence of relatively high chloride concentration in freshwater (about $250 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$ or more) may indicate wastewater pollution (Nayla Hassan Omer,2019). Chlorides may enter surface water from several sources including chloride-containing rock, agricultural runoff, and wastewater. Chloride ions Cl^- in drinking water do not cause any harmful effects on public health. The analysis revealed chloride in sample A ($20.08 \pm 0.40 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$), B (22.17 ± 0.28), C ($26.83 \pm 0.25 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$), D ($17.70 \pm 0.29 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$) and E ($13.93 \pm 0.25 \text{ mg}/\text{L}$).The chloride content of all the samples were within the

recommended standard 250 mg/L by NSDWQ and 200 mg/L by WHO for drinking water.

Nitrate

The presence of nitrates in a water sample could be due to inorganic fertilizers, plants and animal decomposition and wastes which may have percolated the waters over time (Yusuf et al.,2024).Nitrates indicates the presence of fully oxidized organic matter. High nitrate concentrations in drinking water causes blue-baby syndrome in bottle-fed infants (Tongu et al; 2024) .The concentration of nitrate in samples A to D ranges from 0.42 ± 0.01 mg/L to 0.61 ± 0.01 mg/L and were within the recommended standard (50 mg/L) by both NSDWQ and WHO for drinking water. These concentrations have no health implication.

Calcium Hardness

From the result of the analysis, calcium hardness ranges from 15.49 ± 0.42 mg/L to 35.67 ± 0.14 mg/L. The concentrations of calcium carbonate in all the samples were within the recommended standard of 200 mg/L by WHO and 250 mg/L by NSDWQ for drinking water

Dissolved Oxygen (DO)

Natural water contains dissolved solids such as salts of Ca, Mg, Na, K, Fe and traces of heavy metals. This is due to minerals in rocks and soil. But the amount of inorganic dissolved solids is increased due to discharge from industry (Verma,R.M.2012). The results of the analysis revealed the DO of samples A, B, C, D and E to be 5.23 ± 0.15 , 6.17 ± 0.06 , 5.73 ± 0.12 , 6.5 ± 0.17 and 5.57 ± 0.12 all in mg/L respectively. No health based value is recommended, however very high levels of DO may exacerbate corrosion of metal pipes (WHO).

Phosphate

The presence of phosphate in a water source could be attributed to discharges from detergents, animal wastes and related contaminants (Yusuf et al., 2024).The phosphate of the five well water analysed ranged from 7.8 ± 0.11 mg/L to 11.02 ± 0.22 mg/L. These results were higher than 0.05 to 0.09 mg/L that was reported by Yusuf et al., 2024.

Sulphate

The presence of sulfate in drinking-water can cause noticeable taste, and very high levels might cause a laxative effect in unaccustomed consumers.

Taste impairment varies with the nature of the associated cation; taste thresholds have been found to range from 250 mg/l for sodium sulfate to 1000 mg/l for calcium sulfate(WHO). The sulphate contents of the well water samples was 0.91 ± 0.12 mg/L to 4.56 ± 0.6 mg/L and the values were below the recommend standard (100 mg/L) by NSDWQ and (250 mg/L to 1000 mg/L) by WHO for drinking water in 2015 and 2017 respectively.

Ca

Calcium is the fifth most abundant natural element. It enters the freshwater system through the weathering of rocks, especially limestone, and from soil through seepage, leaching and run-off. The concentration of calcium in water depends on the residence time of the water in calcium-rich geologic formations. Undesirable effects due to the presence of calcium in drinking water may result from its contribution to hardness. The Ca content of the water samples analysed ranges from 5.33 ± 0.15 mg/L to 11.33 ± 0.56 mg/L.

Na

Sodium is a common element in the natural environment and is often found in food and drinking water. Sodium salts are generally highly soluble in water and are leached from the terrestrial environment to groundwater and surface water. Sodium salts are not usually toxic because of the efficiency with which mature kidneys excrete sodium s(Lila et al,2023) The taste threshold concentration of sodium in water depends on the associated anion and the temperature of the solution. At room temperature, the average taste threshold for sodium is about 200 mg/L (WHO). The concentration of Na of samples analysed was within 1.9 ± 0.1 mg/L to 3.12 ± 0.08 mg/L and it was within the acceptable limit of 200 mg/L by both NSDWQ and WHO for drinking water in 2015 and 2017 respectively. No health-based guideline value has been derived, as the contribution from drinking-water to daily intake is small faults (WHO).

K

Potassium is an essential element in humans and is seldom, if ever found in drinking water at levels that could be a concern for healthy humans. Potassium occurs widely in the environment including all natural waters. It can also occur in drinking water as a consequence of the use of potassium permanganate as an oxidant in water treatment. Although potassium may cause some health effects in susceptible individuals, potassium intake from drinking water is well below the level at which adverse health effects may occur. Potassium is an essential element and is present in all animal and

plant tissues. (Lila et al,2023).The concentration of the water sample analysed ranges from 0.40 ± 0.03 mg/L to 0.40 ± 0.03 mg/L

Fe

Iron Anaerobic groundwater may contain ferrous iron at concentrations up to several milligrams per litre without discoloration or turbidity in the water when directly pumped from a well. At levels above 0.3 mg/l, iron stains laundry and plumbing fixtures (WHO).The concentrations of iron ranges from 0.16 ± 0.02 mg/L to 0.37 ± 0.02 mg/L. Samples A,B and E were within the recommend standard of 0.3 mg/L for iron by both NSDWQ and WHO for drinking water. While samples C (0.37 ± 0.02 mg/L) and D (0.32 ± 0.02 mg/L) were high. There is usually no noticeable taste at iron concentrations below 0.3 mg/l, although turbidity and colour may develop. No health-based guideline value is proposed for iron (WHO).

Pb

Lead (Pb) is a common metal found throughout the environment in lead - based paint, air, food, and certain types of pottery, porcelain, pewter and in drinking water. Lead can pose a significant risk to human health; it can cause damage to the brain, red blood cells and kidneys. Signs of lead intoxication may include irritability, headaches, kidney damage, dullness, restlessness, etc (Lila et al,2023). Pb was not detected in samples A, B and E but found in C (0.01 mg/L) and D (0.01 mg/L).According to NSDWQ and WHO, 0.01 mg/L of Pb can cause cancer, interfere with vitamin D metabolism, affect development of infants and it can also be toxic to central and pheripheral nervous systems.

Cd

Cadmium is a natural occurring metal, it is a soft silverfish - white metal that is found in the earth's crust and is commonly associated with copper, lead, and zinc ores. Cadmium becomes a problem when an individual is exposed to sources of cadmium through environmental exposure which can be through air, contaminated water, contaminated food, etc. Cadmium contamination of a water source can be through natural erosion of cadmium - containing rocks, industrial dust or waste, fertilizer (contaminant in phosphate rock), mine tailings or spoil, corrosion of galvanized pipes, etc. Cadmium has been linked to kidney disorders, anemia and lung damage. For children, a number of studies show that they are vulnerable to the absorption of cadmium and may be vulnerable to decreased bone strength. Low level exposure to cadmium decrease bone

density and disrupts bone composition. Both shorter, higher exposures and lifetime low level exposures to cadmium can cause kidney disease in adult (Lila et al,2023). Cd was not detected in samples A, B and D. Sample C contained 0.01 mg/L of Cd and was higher than 0.003 mg/L recommended by both NSDWQ and WHO for drinking water. The sample C will be toxic to kidney

Cr

From table 2 above, 0.02 mg/L and 0.01 mg/L of Cr was found in samples C and D respectively while it was below the detection limit in samples A,B and E. The values obtained in this analysis were within the acceptable limit of 0.05 mg/L by both NSDWQ and WHO for drinking water.

Zn

Zinc imparts an undesirable astringent taste to water at a taste threshold concentration of about 4 mg/l (as zinc sulfate). Water containing zinc at concentrations in excess of 3-5 mg/l may appear opalescent and develop a greasy film on boiling (WHO). The concentration of Zn in table 2 above showed a range of 0.29±0.01 mg/L to 0.42±0.02 mg/L. Zn contents of all sample analysed were within the acceptable standard of 3 mg/L by NSDWQ and above 0.1 mg/L by WHO for drinking water.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The analysis revealed that some physicochemical parameter of some of the well water obtained from Ujeh in Ibaji LGA, kogi state were low, within and high when compared with NSDWQ (2015) and WHO (2022) standard for domestic water. High turbidity concentrations of samples C and D were as a result of total dissolved concentrations as seen in the concentration of Fe, Pb and Cr in both samples C and D, and Cd in sample C that were high. Consumption of water of well C and D will cause cancer because of the high concentration of lead while water of well C will be toxic to kidney due to the high concentration of Cd. The people of Ujeh should be informed of the risk in consuming water of well C and D and bacteriological assessment of water from all wells analysed should be carried out to be sure if the water is safe for drinking and other domestic purposes. Government should drill borehole for the people.

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